

FIDAMC

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Manufacture process of structural upper skin panel highly integrated in carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic material

AIRBUS

TWENTY-THIRD INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS (ICCM23)

Manufacture process of structural upper skin panel highly integrated in carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic material

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INDEX

1. INTRODUCTION
2. IN SITU CONSOLIDATION PROCESS BY AFP
3. OUTCOME THERMOPLASTIC PROJET
4. CONCLUSIONS
5. WAY FORWARD

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Motivation

Upper skin panel

- Cost reduction
- Weight saving
- Mechanical properties improvements
- Reduced moisture absorption
- Reprocessed material
- Welding
- Thermo-forming

1. INTRODUCTION

1.2 Target OUTCOME Thermoplastic Project

Regional FTB#2
Upper Skin

Upper skin panel: 6 x "T" stringer configuration

1. INTRODUCTION

1.3 OUTCOME PROJECTS CHALLENGES

- Eco-efficient process: reduction of consumption, weight, costs, etc.
- Manufacture with high performance thermoplastic materials.
- Improvement AFP Thermoplastic
- Development of tools for the manufacture of stringers and automatic lamination.
- Out of autoclave processes:
 - Development of processes to manufacture T stringers
 - Improved co-consolidation process, automatic lamination by in situ consolidation in one step for large structures.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.4 Background

FIDAMC has been involved since 2010 in the research of thermoplastic matrix composite materials together with AIRBUS DS and MTORRES.

Some of the research projects carried out are detailed:

- **ICARO & TARGET project, CENIT national programmes of CDTI.**

- **ISINTHER project; CLEANSKY, 7th Framework Programme.**

1. INTRODUCTION

1.4 Background

- **GRA project, CLEANSKY, 7th Framework Programme.**

- **OUTCOME Thermoplastic Project; CLEANSKY 2, 7th Framework Programme.**

2. IN SITU CONSOLIDATION PROCESS BY AFP

2.1 Advantages of automatic lamination

SUPPORTING PRODUCTION RATES
REDUCED LABOUR/MATERIAL COSTS
LARGE COMPOSITE COMPONENTS
REDUCED SCRAP
REDUCED MANUFACTURING TIME
ACCURATE FIBER PLACEMENT AT ANY ANGLE
AUTOMATIC DEBULKING
FAST SPEED OF MATERIAL DEPOSITION (>10lb/hr) [Hand lay-up 2,5lb/hr]
REPEATABILITY OF RESULTS/ACCURACY AND REPEATABILITY OF THE PRODUCTION PROCESS

2. IN SITU CONSOLIDATION PROCESS BY AFP

2.2 Thermoplastic Consolidation

Consolidation of melt-fusible thermoplastics consists of heating, consolidation, and cooling, as depicted schematically in the figure below. As with thermoset composites, the main processing variables are time (t), temperature (T), and pressure (P).

Fuente: F._C._Campbell-Structural_Composite_Materials-ASM_International_(2010)

2. IN SITU CONSOLIDATION PROCESS BY AFP

2. 3 AFP Thermoplastic evolution

2. IN SITU CONSOLIDATION PROCESS BY AFP

2. 3 AFP Thermoplastic evolution

2022-2025

New Head development to increase production rates

2017-2023

OUTCOME_UPPER SKIN

2. IN SITU CONSOLIDATION PROCESS BY AFP

2.4 AFP Thermoplastic

3. OUTCOME THERMOPLASTIC PROJECT

Regional FTB#2 Upper Skin

Material	APC2/AS4_SOLVAY (1/4" y 300 mm)
Stringers	Oven forming_T stringers without rivets
Skin	Co-consolidation process by in situ consolidation (ISC) by automated fibre (AFP)

Upper skin panel: 6 x "T" stringers configuration

3. OUTCOME THERMOPLASTIC PROJECT

3. OUTCOME THERMOPLASTIC PROJECT

3.1 Coupons Test

- Material allowable_ 70W_120W
- Residual strength after impact
- Bolted joints
- Lightning strike protection
- Residual stress test plan
- Co-consolidation test plan

3. OUTCOME THERMOPLASTIC PROJECT

3.2 Details tests

CRIPPLING

SRO DETAIL

3. OUTCOME THERMOPLASTIC PROJECT

3.3 Sub-components Tests

Skin Panel

SRO Sub-Component

3. OUTCOME THERMOPLASTIC PROJECT

3.4 Upper Skin: Manufacturing process

3. OUTCOME THERMOPLASTIC PROJECT

3.4 Upper Skin: Manufacturing process

STRINGERS

AFP SKIN PANEL

3. OUTCOME THERMOPLASTIC PROJECT

3.5 Upper Skin

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. **Thermoplastics are an opportunity to reduce manufacturing costs and obtain more efficient processes.**
2. **Cost savings of 15% and structural weight savings of 9% compared to the metallic equivalent.**
3. **It has been proven that by increasing the dimensions of the parts to be manufactured, technological challenges have been growing in the design and manufacture of the tooling.**
4. **Mathematical models are needed to simulate the behaviors of residual stress structures to adjust the designs of the tools.**
5. **A control system in automatic lamination processes, with high-performance thermoplastic materials, are essential to give robustness to the process.**
6. **Reversible processes**
7. **Highly recyclable, lower environmental impact throughout the entire life cycle, from the generation of raw material, manufacturing, operation and end of life.**

5. WAY FORWARD

AUTOMATIC LAMINATION PROCESS

- Improve productivity ratios in one step
- Reduction of residual stresses
- Increase the consolidation degree in AFP by in situ consolidation.

STRINGER MANUFACTURING PROCESS

- To study alternative manufacturing processes for stringer in order to improve the quality and production rates.
- Analyze the final geometry of stringer not clamped to correct springback and torsions on tooling.

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THANK YOU

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